

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude And Practices of Tobacco Cessation Counselling And Nicotine Replacement Therapy Among Dental Professionals

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Abstract

The tobacco epidemic is a significant global health challenge, with over one-third of Indian adults using tobacco in some form. Despite the known adverse effects of tobacco on oral and general health, many individuals continue its use due to nicotine addiction. Nicotine Replacement Therapy (NRT) is an effective pharmacological approach to aid in tobacco cessation by alleviating withdrawal symptoms. This study assesses the knowledge, attitude, and practices of dental professionals regarding tobacco cessation counseling (TCC) and NRT. A survey was conducted among 250 dental students, including interns, postgraduates, and faculty members, to evaluate their training, confidence, and practices in TCC and NRT. The results revealed that while all participants recognized the harmful effects of tobacco, only 28% were trained in TCC and 54% were aware of NRT agents. A significant portion of participants lacked confidence in prescribing NRT due to insufficient training. This study underscores the need for enhanced curriculum, certification courses, and continuous education programs to improve the competency of dental professionals in tobacco cessation efforts.

Keywords : Tobacco Cessation Counseling (TCC), Nicotine Replacement Therapy (NRT), Dental Professionals, Tobacco Epidemic, Oral Health, Addiction, Pharmacotherapy, Dental Education, Survey, India

Introduction

Globally, one of the greatest health challenges of today is tobacco epidemic. According To global adult tobacco survey (GATS), WHO India (2020) revealed that over one third of Indian adults (22.3%) use tobacco in some form.^{1,2} Tobacco has deleterious effects on oral and general health, regardless of which, many people consume tobacco due to their addiction towards it. Both smoked and smokeless forms of tobacco contain nicotine, a highly addictive chemical, making it difficult for habituated tobacco users to quit.³ This urge towards tobacco is due to the presence of an extremely compelling psychoactive drug nicotine 11-methyl-2 pyrrolidine in it. Over time, users become dependent on nicotine and suddenly stopping produces physical as well as psychological withdrawal symptoms.⁴ Tobacco dependence is a chronic condition that often requires repeated interventions. As Smokers are 7–10 times more likely to develop oral cancers as compared to those who have never smoked.^{5,6} So, Dentists play an important role in TCC as dentist are first to observe oral changes and can educate patients. DCI mandates TCC training during internship. TCC aims for psychological cou-

nselling of tobacco consumers but along with this pharmacological approach should also be practised so as to increase quit rates.⁷ Pharmacotherapy like nicotine replacement therapy (NRT) can help reduce the symptoms of nicotine withdrawal, which makes quitting easier. The study is conducted to assess the level of the knowledge, attitude, and effectiveness of dental students and professionals towards tobacco cessation & to assess if the dental practitioner is able to educate, motivate, and counsel the patient with tobacco dependence.

Materials and Methods

250 dental students including interns, postgraduate, and faculty members of Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College And Research Center, Ghaziabad, U.P were enrolled in the study. A printed survey proforma of 29 questions, divided into four sections: Demographic details (question nos. 1–3), knowledge (question nos. 4–18) -if dental practitioners

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are trained for tobacco cessation counselling (TCC), NRT'S, attitude (question nos. 19–25) - if dental practitioners think counselling/NRT/drugs can help patients quit tobacco and practices (question nos. 26–29) - if dental practitioners practice TCC at their workplace. The questionnaire comprised 29 questions to evaluate the attitude, awareness of smoking cessation, willingness to provide tobacco cessation services [Table 1] which had to be answered by each respondent. The data obtained was then entered in Microsoft Excel and descriptive analysis was done.

Table 1: The questionnaire for the study -

Questionnaire

Demographic data

1. Gender- Male Female (Tick the appropriate option.)
2. Current Designation- Intern/Postgraduate student/Dental faculty (Tick the appropriate option.)
3. Experience in months-

Knowledge

4. Are you aware of the role of tobacco in oral cancer and general health?

a. Yes	b. No
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5. Can you identify the lesions caused by tobacco products?

a. Yes	b. No
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6. Are you trained for tobacco cessation counselling (TCC) in terms of questions to be asked and providing guidance to the addict?

a. Yes	b. No
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7. Do you know about 5As and 5Rs in Tobacco Cessation Counselling?

a. Yes	b. No
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8. Do you know about agents used as Nicotine Replacement Therapy (NRT)?

a. Yes	b. No
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9. If yes, name the product used as NRT.....
10. Do you know how to prescribe NRT?

a. Yes	b. No
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11. Do you know about the side effects of NRT?

a. Yes	b. No
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12. If yes, name them.....
13. Do you know about the medications for deaddiction?

a. Yes	b. No
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14. If yes, name them.....
15. Do you know about the side effects of medications used?

a. Yes	b. No
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16. If yes, name them.....
17. Are you aware about the organisations/NGOs that help patients quit tobacco?

a. Yes	b. No
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18. Do you know that each dental institute across India has a Tobacco Cessation Cell to help the patients?

a. Yes	b. No
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Attitude

19. Do you ask the patients about history of or current use of tobacco?

a. Yes	b. No
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20. Do you think it is your responsibility to counsel patient in private set-up and in dental institutions?

a. Yes	b. No
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21. Do you think counselling/NRT/drugs will help patients quit tobacco?

a. Yes	b. No
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22. Are you concerned that such counselling in dentistry may upset the dentist-patient relationship in private practice?

a. Yes	b. No
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23. Are you willing to spare time to advise patients about tobacco cessation in your professional career?

a. Yes	b. No
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24. Will you be interested in gaining knowledge about TCC?

a. Yes	b. No
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25. What are patient's main reasons for wanting to quit?
 - Health concerns
 - Cost
 - Family/friends
 - Support groups

Practices

26. Do you practise TCC at your workplace in terms of counselling/NRT/Drug prescription?

a. Yes	b. No
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27. If yes, are you satisfied with the results?

a. Yes	b. No
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28. If no, tick for the appropriate reason/reasons-
 - Not interested
 - It is not money-fetching as other dental treatments
 - Belief that TCC doesn't really help patients
 - Lack of time
 - Lack of knowledge and training for TCC and NRT
 - Lack of resources
29. What challenges are faced by patient in quitting tobacco?
 - Craving
 - Weight gain
 - Stress management
 - Social situations

Results & Discussion

Demographic data

Out of the total 250 participants in the study, 67 were dental faculty members, 52 were postgraduate students and 131 were interns. 86 males and 164 females participated in the study. Mean experience of the candidates was 24.81 months.

All participants (100%) were aware of the role of tobacco products in oral cancer and general health and identify the lesions caused by tobacco products. Only (28%) candidates were trained for TCC in terms of questions to be asked and giving guidance to the addict; Q6 [Table 1]. 54% - Over half of the dental

professionals belong to Group 1 who were aware of NRT agents ;Q8 [Table 2]. Nicotex chewing gum was known by most people (35%), as it is easily available in local chemists' shops and advertised more as compared to other agents. only 36% knew how to prescribe NRT. Most of the candidates have a positive attitude toward tobacco cessation but do not feel confident to prescribe NRT due to no training or not being updated about NRT. (40%) knew about the side effects of NRT like indigestion, headache, mood swings, bad taste, etc. Besides NRT agents, only (28%) knew about the drugs used for de-addiction. Q13 [Table 3]. Bupropion and Varenicline were known by most of the candidates. All candidates felt that it is their responsibility to counsel the patients for de-addiction; Q20 [Table 4]. (90%) felt that such anti-tobacco counselling might upset doctor-patient relationship in a private set-up Q22 [Table 5]. Hence, many of them did not try to counsel the patients and prioritised dental issues. (30%) were currently practising TCC at the workplace in terms of counselling or NRT or drugs Q26 [Table 6] The survey found that 30% of dental professionals regularly provide tobacco cessation counselling, nicotine replacement therapy, or drug prescriptions to their patients at the workplace. However, 60% of participants reported a lack of knowledge and training for tobacco cessation counseling and nicotine replacement therapy as a barrier to providing these services.

Few challenges are faced by patient in quitting tobacco like craving (64%) Q29 [TABLE 7], but none of them were satisfied as the patients were often lost to follow-ups. This can be overcome by the use of behaviour modification approaches for the patients. In an institutional set-up, customised short counselling visits, use of audio-visual aids, clubbing dental visits with counselling appointments, personalised reminder messages, involving family members for help and offering small rewards to the patients will surely help in increasing patient follow-up visits. While Other participants did not practice it; the main reason being lack of knowledge and training for TCC and NRT.

Results

Table 1 : Q6. Frequency and percentage of participants trained for TCC

Group Frequency Percent

1 70 28.0
2 180 72.0

Total 250 100.0

Group 1 ■ Group 2 ■

The pie chart shows the frequency and percentage of participants who have received training for TCC. (28%) of the dental professionals belong to Group 1, Trained for TCC in terms of questions to be asked & giving guidance to the addict indicating a fair level of training among the participants.

Graph 1 showing Only 28% candidates were trained for TCC ;

Table 2: Q8. Frequency and percentage of participants who know about various agents used as NRT.

Group Frequency Percent

1 136 54.0
2 114 46.0
Total 250 100.0

Group 1 ■ Group 2 ■

The pie chart shows the frequency and percentage of participants who know about various nicotine replacement therapy (NRT) agents. Over half (54%) of the dental professionals belong to Group 1 who were aware of NRT agents – Nicotex chewing gums

Graph 2 showing 54% of the dental professionals were aware of NRT agents ;

Table 3: Q13. Frequency and percentage of participants who know about the drugs used for tobacco de-addiction

Group Frequency Percent

1 71 28.0
2 179 72.0
Total 250 100.0

The pie chart shows the frequency and percentage of participants who Know About De-addiction Drugs- Bupropion, Varenicline. 28% of the dental professionals belong to Group 1 who knew about the drugs used for Tobacco de-addiction.

Graph 3 showing 28% knew about the drugs used for Tobacco de-addiction.

Table 4:Q20. Frequency and percentage of participants who think it is their responsibility to counsel the patients.

Group	Frequency	Percent
1	250	100
2	00	00
Total	250	100.0

Graph 4 showing All candidates felt that it is their responsibility to counsel the patients for de-addiction;

Table 5 : Q22. Frequency and percentage of participants who think that such counselling in dentistry may upset the dentist-patient relationship.

Group	Frequency	Percent
1	224	90.0
2	26	10.0
Total	250	100.0

Graph 4 showing All candidates felt that it is their responsibility to counsel the patients for de-addiction;

Table 5:Q22. Frequency and percentage of participants who think that such counselling in dentistry may upset the dentist-patient relationship.

Group	Frequency	Percent
1	224	90.0
2	26	10.0
Total	250	100.0

The pie chart shows the frequency and percentage of participants who felt that such anti-tobacco counselling might upset doctor-patient relationship in a private set-up. 90% of the dental professionals belong to Group 1 who felt that such anti-tobacco counselling might upset doctor-patient relationship in a private set-up.

Graph 5 showing 90% felt that such anti-tobacco counselling might upset doctor-patient relationship in a private set-up .

Table 6:Q26. Frequency and percentage of participants who practise TCC at workplace in terms of counselling/NRT/drug prescription

Group	Frequency	Percent
1 Practice TCC	75	30.0
2, because of lack of resources	00	00
2, because of lack of time	00	00
2, TCC doesn't help	2510	100.0

2, because of lack of knowledge and training for TCC and NRT	150	60
	100	40
Total	250	100.0

The pie chart shows the frequency and percentage of participants who practice tobacco cessation counseling, nicotine replacement therapy, or drug prescriptions to their patients at the workplace. 30% of the dental professionals belong to Group 1 who practice tobacco cessation counseling, nicotine replacement therapy. While group 2 (10%) felt that, TCC doesn't help. Whereas group 3 (60%) do not practice TCC because of lack of knowledge and training for TCC and NRT.

Graph 6 showing 30% of dental professionals who practice tobacco cessation counseling, nicotine replacement therapy, or drug prescriptions to their patients at the workplace.

Table 7: Q29. what challenges are faced by patient in quitting tobacco?

Group	Frequency	Percent
1 Craving	161	64.0
2, Weight gain	42	16.8
2, Stress management	65	36
2, Social situations	198	79.2
Total	250	100.0

The pie chart shows the frequency and percentage of participants (64%) who faced challenges like craving in quitting tobacco when asked by dental professionals. 64% of the patients belong to Group 1 who faced challenges like craving. While group 2 (2%) patients felt that challenges like Weight gain are faced by patient in quitting tobacco whereas group 3 (36%) required stress management techniques. And group 4 (8%) patients felt that challenges like Social situations affect in quitting tobacco.

Graph 7 showing 64% challenges like craving are faced by patients in quitting tobacco when asked by dental professionals.

Discussion

Dental professionals role in TCC is that they can easily recognize patient's tobacco status owing to the oral implications such as staining, habit-related lesions like leukoplakia, oral cancer; can effectively manage tobacco dependence and provide counselling & support to patients.

Tobacco cessation is a multidisciplinary approach. There are 5 major steps (the "5 As") Ask, Advise, Assess, Assist and Arrange in tobacco cessation services. It is important for the dental practitioner to "Ask" the patient if he or she uses tobacco, "Advise" him or her to quit, "Assess" willingness to make a quit attempt, "Assist" the patient in making a quit attempt, and "Arrange" for follow-up contacts to prevent relapse. and the 5 Rs are Relevance, Risk, Rewards, Repetitions and Roadblocks.

Acc. To study by Shete AV et al (2023) only (22%) candidates were trained for TCC, whereas we found 28% participants trained for TCC.

Acc. To study by Shete AV et al (2023), 71 clinicians out of 200 (35.5%) knew how to prescribe NRT; the other 129 clinicians (64.5%) had no clue about it. Almost similarly in our study 36% knew to prescribe NRT, although 56% were not aware of NRT.

Conclusion and Key Points

Majority of oral physicians are actively participating in recording the patient habit and counselling by means of warning and advising to quit the habit. There is limited stress on pharmacological and behavioural interventions and referral in case of high dependence and limited additional training regarding cessation. Thus, there is a need for alteration in the curriculum. More Certification courses by government of India are needed to be implemented in BDS Postgraduate course and more CDE programs to enhance the knowledge and effective role in tobacco cessation.

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